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Human vulnerability in the Past: reflections on an interdisciplinary research Experience

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Title: Human vulnerability in the Past: reflections on an interdisciplinary research Experience

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Abstract: This presentation is based on an ongoing doctoral research project entitled “Human Vulnerability in Written Sources: Exploring Sociobiological Determinants in the Nineteenth-Century City of Porto (1832–1899)”. The project seeks to explore the multiple dimensions of human vulnerability through the analysis of a broad range of historical sources. It is also linked to the bioarchaeological and archaeological study of the cemetery of the Venerable Third Order of Our Lady of Carmel (BeFrail – Porto in Times of Cholera and War project). This research has proven to be a rewarding yet highly challenging experience.

The presentation will focus on these challenges, which have at times led to valuable discoveries and fruitful exchanges of knowledge, and at others to moments of doubt and uncertainty. Its main objective is to highlight the potential of interdisciplinary approaches in historical research, while also addressing the challenges they entail—challenges that are not always fully considered during the design and planning of research projects.

Keywords: Human vulnerability; Interdisciplinary research; Historical sources; Nineteenth-century Porto.